

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Hazard maps of spatio-temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides in the pilot sites according to actual and future climatic conditions

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General targets focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the developed method for estimating the spatio-temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides in the selected pilot-sites (Versa-Scuropasso, Ardivestra, Tidone Pavese) according to actual and future climatic conditions. This method allows to produce hazard maps for the probability of occurrence of shallow landslides and to give indications on the change in hazard towards these phenomena from actual to future climatic scenarios. The method is based on predisposing factors of shallow landslides proneness, derived from geological, geomorphological and land uses datasets, integrated by triggering factors derived by information on actual and future rainfall conditions and soil saturation degree trends. This deliverable shows the preliminary results of the application of this method, aimed to deliver scientifically grounded assessments of shallow slope instabilities-prone areas in the Oltrepò Pavese, ultimately reducing risk costs and improving land use management.

A) METHOD FOR SPATIO-TEMPORAL PROBABILITY OF OCCURRENCE OF SHALLOW LANDSLIDES

The method for the assessment of spatio-temporal probability of occurrence towards shallow landslides is based on the data-driven model proposed in Bordoni et al. (2021), improved by considering soil saturation degree at the typical depth of shallow landslides sliding surface (1 m from the ground) within the set of the triggering factors considered in the temporal part of the model.

The method has been developed and applied in four test-sites of Oltrepò Pavese (Ardivestra, Versa, Scuropasso, Tidone Pavese), representative of the different geological, geomorphological and land use contexts that are more prone to shallow landsliding in this area.

The developed methodology is described in the following section.

Spatial probability of occurrence of shallow landslides

The spatial probability of occurrence of shallow landslides (susceptibility) is calculated with a data-driven model based on Multiadaptive Regression Splines (MARS), considering eleven predictors that have been selected considering their influence to identify areas where the underlying conditions would lead most likely to landslides: slope angle (SL), slope aspect (ASP), profile curvature (PRO), catchment area (CA), catchment slope (CS), topographic wetness index (TWI), topographic position index (TPI), terrain ruggedness index (TRI), land use (LU), bedrock geology (GEO).

The geomorphological and hydrological predictors (SL, ASP, PRO, CA, CS, TWI, TPI, TRI) were obtained from a 5 m resolution Digital Elevation Model created using LiDAR data. The data was prepared by the Italian Ministry for Environment, Land, and Sea in 2008 and 2010. The source of the land use data is the DUSAF of 2007 from the Lombardy Region, at a scale of 1:10000. The GEO map is based on the bedrock lithological map at a scale of 1:10000, as described by Meisina et al. (2006).

The response variable of the model is represented by the inventory of shallow landslides occurred in each test-site since 2009. The spatial location of the events are identified through field observations, analysis of optical images, and Italian Landslides Inventory (IFFI) (only for Tidone Pavese area).

Once created the database of predictor variables, a variance inflation factor (VIF) (Bui et al., 2016) is set on numerical predictors to assess the collinearity between predictors. If the VIF is equal or more than 10, they are collinear to each other. With the excluding collinear variables, other variables are included in the model.

After collinearity test, a comprehensive database is created, including pixels associated with shallow landslides and an equivalent number of randomly chosen non-shallow landslide pixels. This dataset was then divided into two subsets, allocating two-thirds as the training set for building the model and the remaining one-third as a test set for model accuracy evaluation.

A 100-fold bootstrap procedure is applied in the training and test selection process. The resulting 100 bootstrap models extended predictions across the entire study area, producing a spatial probability distribution of shallow landslides for each pixel. Mean values from these distributions is used to create the final shallow landslides susceptibility map.

The performance of the susceptibility model is assessed using

- the Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC) for the study area;
- the 4-fold plot indexes, calculating the false negative (predicted no triggering event, where or when there is triggering event), false positive (predicted triggering event, where or when there is no triggering event), true positive (predicted triggering event. Where or when there is triggering event) and true negative (predicted no triggering event, where or when there is no triggering event) indexes;
- the distribution of areas across different susceptibility classes, according to the following classes: (i) low ($0 < \text{susceptibility} \leq 0.25$); (ii) medium-low ($0.25 < \text{susceptibility} \leq 0.50$); (iii) medium-high ($0.50 < \text{susceptibility} \leq 0.75$); (iv) high ($0.75 \leq \text{susceptibility} \leq 1$)

Figure 1 shows the obtained susceptibility maps for the test-sites, while Table 1 shows the values of indexes for the predictive capability of the model and the distribution of the susceptibility values across different classes for each test-site.

The obtained susceptibility models have a good predictive capability, as testified by AUROC higher than 0.89, true positive higher than 89% and true negative higher than 79%. The sectors

classified with medium-high and high spatial probability of occurrence range between 13 and 22%.

Table 1: Performance of the models and distribution of the classes for the models of spatial probability of occurrence

Test-site	AUROC (-)	True positive (%)	True negative (%)	False positive (%)	False negative (%)	Spatial probability of occurrence			
						Low (%)	Medium-low (%)	Medium-high (%)	High (%)
Ardivestra	0.90	89	81	19	11	66	12	12	10
Tidone Pavese	0.93	89	79	21	11	75	12	5	8
Versa-Scuropasso	0.89	91	82	18	9	61	19	12	8

Figure 1: Maps of spatial probability of occurrence for the test-sites

Temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides

The temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides, considering all the test-sites, is derived through another data-driven approach, again based on MARS algorithm, aiming to

predict the probability of shallow failures triggering at daily resolution. The predictors of the model are represented by 1) the cumulative rainfall amounts in different periods (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 15, 30, and 60 days); 2) the soil saturation degree of the soil horizon where typically shallow landslides sliding surfaces develop, measured at 0:00 UTC of a particular day.

As regards the rainfall data, field hourly rainfall data collected from 21 rain gauges (belonging to ARPA Lombardia and ARPAE Emilia Romagna) over the region of Oltrepò Pavese are considered, (Fig. 12) transforming hourly data to daily rainfall amount. On the other hand, ERA5-Land service, which is product of Copernicus Climate Data Store service (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>) is used to retrieve soil moisture measures, utilized to derive the saturation degree in correspondence to each rain gauge station. Soil moisture of the layer 28-100 cm is considered, since it is in correspondence of the typical depth of the shallow landslides sliding surface in the area and has the highest correspondence with the identification of the typical hydrological triggering conditions of slope failures (Bordoni et al., 2023). Rainfall and soil moisture datasets are reconstructed for the period 1993-2023. Moreover, a daily inventory of the triggering conditions of shallow landslides in the same time span is reconstructed for the study area, through reports of public administrations, newspapers, and online chronicles.

The predictors and the response variable are merged in a matrix for the application of the data-driven methodology. Models are built, each considering a couple of the rainfall predictors together with the saturation degree. Each model is reconstructed through the same statistical approach implemented for estimating the spatial probability of occurrence of shallow landslides. Thus, the models are reconstructed since a database, consisting of all triggering days and the same number of days without triggering, subdivided into 2 subsets, corresponding to the training (2/3 of this dataset) and the test sets (the remaining 1/3 of the dataset). The 100-fold bootstrap procedure is employed to generate 100 fitted bootstrap scenarios and extend the prediction to the entire database.

As there are 45 different scenarios for combinations of cumulated rainfall (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 15, 30, and 60 days) and saturation degree at the depth of 1m, a semi-automatic method is used to choose the best model for the final output. The optimal combination is identified as the one with the highest value of Efficiency (EF), calculated according to the following equation (eq. 1):

$$EF = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

, where TP, TN, FP, and FN represent True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives, and False Negatives respectively.

Comprehensive analysis of all possible combinations reveals that a combination of 2-day cumulative rainfall, 5-day cumulative rainfall, and the saturation degree (Sat-degree) at 1m has the highest efficiency (94.86%) and is selected as the model for the temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides.

Table 2: Efficiency of the different combinations adopted for the models of the temporal probability of occurrence

Combination	P2-P3-Sat-1m	P2-P4-Sat-1m	P2-P5-Sat-1m	P2-P6-Sat-1m	P2-P7-Sat-1m	P2-P10-Sat-1m	P2-P14-Sat-1m
EF	94.26%	94.21%	94.86%	94.49%	94.47%	94.11%	94.01%
Combination	P2-P30-Sat-1m	P2-P60-Sat-1m	P3-P4-Sat-1m	P3-P5-Sat-1m	P3-P6-Sat-1m	P3-P7-Sat-1m	P3-P10-Sat-1m
EF	94.54%	93.80%	93.60%	92.96%	93.84%	94.19%	94.52%
Combination	P3P14-Sat-1m	P3P30-Sat-1m	P3-P60-Sat-1m	P4-P5-Sat-1m	P4-P6-Sat-1m	P4-P7-Sat-1m	P4-P10-Sat-1m
EF	93.82%	93.89%	93.45%	93.08%	94.08%	93.40%	92.85%
Combination	P4-P14-Sat-1m	P4-P30-Sat-1m	P4-P60-Sat-1m	P5-P6-Sat-1m	P5-P7-Sat-1m	P5-P10-Sat-1m	P5-P14-Sat-1m
EF	91.35%	92.63%	93.71%	91.97%	92.69%	93.12%	92.48%
Combination	P7-P10-Sat-1m	P7-P14-Sat-1m	P7-P30-Sat-1m	P7-P60-Sat-1m	P10-P14-Sat-1m	P10-P30-Sat-1m	P10-P60-Sat-1m
EF	91.25%	90.22%	89.75%	90.73%	90.52%	92.09%	90.23%
Combination	P5-P30-Sat-1m	P5-P60-Sat-1m	1m P6-P7-Sat-1m P6	P10-Sat-1m	P6-P14-Sat-1m	P6-P30-Sat-1m	P6-P60-Sat-1m
EF	91.38%	92.73%	91.61%	92.06%	90.50%	90.80%	92.23%
Combination	P14-P30-Sat-1m	P14-P60-Sat-1m	P30-P60-Sat-1m				
EF	86.60%	88.38%	84.69%				

Spatio-Temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides: the Dynamic Landslides Probability Index (DLPI)

According to the method proposed in Bordoni et al. (2021), the spatio-temporal probability of occurrence of shallow landslides in a test-site for a particular day is obtained multiplying the daily temporal probability of occurrence and the map of the spatial probability of occurrence (susceptibility, defining a Dynamic Landslides Probability Index (DLPI). This index is calculated as a joint probability component ensured by independence assumption, that is valid since the two data-driven models do not consider the same predictor variables (Vasu et al. 2016).

Examples of maps of DLPI are shown in Figure 2. DLPI maps allow to show the evolution, in space and in time, of the probability of occurrence of shallow landslides in an area, during a particular rainfall event or for a more prolonged rainy period, representing a reliable tool to

identify which hydrological conditions can lead to landslides triggering and where the slope failures can develop.

Figure 2: Example of maps of Dynamic Landslides Probability Index, for the period 15-20 January 2014 in Tidone Pavese test-site

B) HAZARD MAPS OF SHALLOW LANDSLIDES IN THE PILOT SITES ACCORDING TO ACTUAL AND FUTURE CLIMATIC CONDITIONS

Input data and scenarios

Shallow landslides hazard maps for each pilot site were obtained using the approach of DLPI, multiplying the spatial and the temporal probabilities of occurrence, considering different return times (Lee et al., 2021; Park et al., 2022).

For each pilot site, the distribution of spatial probability of occurrence (susceptibility map) is considered as the same for each scenario. Instead, the temporal probability of occurrence at daily resolution changes according to rainfall and soil saturation conditions of each reconstructed scenario.

Following a precautionary approach, hazard scenarios are reconstructed considering the worst soil hydrological conditions provoking shallow landslides triggering in the study area, corresponding to a saturation degree of 1 as estimated by modelling the temporal probability of

occurrence of past events. Furthermore, 5-day cumulative rainfall is considered equal to the median value (73 mm) of the set of past triggering events in the study areas for each scenario. Thus, the reconstructed scenarios differ for the values of 2-day cumulative rainfall, estimated for the following return times: 2, 5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200 years. These rainfall amounts are estimated by an extreme value analysis, where the maximum rainfall event in a given year, is considered to follow a generalized extreme value distribution (Coles et al., 2001). The Gumbel distribution (extreme value type I) is, then, adopted to estimate the temporal probability. The reconstruction of this distribution is done considering rainfall databases covering a period of at least 30 years.

Thus, for actual climatic conditions, the closest rain gauge to each test-site with at least 30 years observation period is considered: for Versa and Scuropasso and Ardivestra catchments, Torre degli Alberi-Fortunago rain gauge (ARPA Lombardia monitoring network; observation period: 1961-2023); for Tidone Pavese catchment Romagnese rain gauge (ARPAE Emilia Romagna monitoring network; observation period: 1987-2023). Table 3 lists the values of 2-days cumulative rainfall amounts at different return times obtained from these time-series.

Table 3: 2-days cumulative rainfall amounts at different return times for actual climatic conditions

Return time year	2-days cumulative rainfall - Versa and Scuropasso and Ardivestra catchments mm	2-days cumulative rainfall – Tidone Pavese catchment mm
2	65.1	69.7
5	91.4	88.5
10	108.9	100.9
25	131.0	116.7
50	147.3	128.3
75	156.8	135.1
100	163.6	139.9
150	173.0	146.7
200	179.8	151.5

Instead, simulated meteorological data, furnished by Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) in the frame of NODES project, are used for future climatic scenarios. In particular, synthetic 2-day cumulative rainfall time series were created up to 2070 according to 2 different scenarios of greenhouse gas concentrations RCP (Meinshausen et al., 2011). RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios exhibit a stabilisation in the emissions of greenhouse gases or a rapid increase in these emissions, respectively.

For each test-site, 2-day cumulative rainfall time-series of all the cells fallen in a catchment are reconstructed and averaged to obtain the mean time-series of predicted 2-day cumulative rainfalls in the period 2025-2070, for both RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. Thus, the same Gumbel distribution of the maximum yearly measures is adopted to extract the values of 2-day

cumulative rainfalls at the different selected return times (2, 5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200 years). Tables 4 and 5 lists the values of 2-days cumulative rainfall amounts at different return times obtained from projected future scenarios time-series according to RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, respectively.

Table 4: 2-days cumulative rainfall amounts at different return times for future climatic conditions according to RCP 4.5

Return time year	2-days cumulative rainfall - Versa and Scuropasso catchments mm	2-days cumulative rainfall - Ardivestra catchment mm	2-days cumulative rainfall - Tidone Pavese catchment mm
2	51.0	51.7	63.0
5	66.4	78.0	80.5
10	76.6	90.1	92.1
25	89.4	109.4	106.8
50	99.0	123.8	117.7
75	104.5	132.1	124.0
100	108.5	138.0	128.5
150	114.0	146.4	134.8
200	117.9	152.2	139.3

Table 5: 2-days cumulative rainfall amounts at different return times for future climatic conditions according to RCP 8.5

Return time year	2-days cumulative rainfall - Versa and Scuropasso catchments mm	2-days cumulative rainfall - Ardivestra catchment mm	2-days cumulative rainfall - Tidone Pavese catchment mm
2	46.9	48.6	61.3
5	61.6	63.1	78.1
10	71.3	72.7	89.3
25	83.6	84.8	103.4
50	92.7	93.7	113.8
75	98.0	98.9	119.9
100	101.7	102.6	124.2
150	107.0	107.8	130.3
200	110.7	111.5	134.6

The combination between spatial and temporal probability of occurrence allow to obtain hazard maps for rainfall-induced shallow landslides, representing the distribution of the probability of occurrence of shallow landslides for each test-site in correspondence of each return time.

Hazard maps

Examples of the preliminary hazard maps reconstructed for actual and future climatic scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) are shown in Figures 3, 4 and 5 for Tidone Pavese catchment.

The reconstructed preliminary maps represent a useful tool to identify the distribution of the most prone sectors towards shallow landsliding according to rainfall events with different return times, furnishing important information also for land use planning and risk mitigation and management. Furthermore, they represent the evolution and the variation on shallow landslides probability of occurrence according to different future climatic scenarios, thanks to the comparison between maps with same return times reconstructed for a pilot site for actual and projected future climatic conditions.

Figure 3: Hazard maps of Tidone Pavese test-site for different return times (Tr) according to actual climatic scenario

Figure 4: Hazard maps of Tidone Pavese test-site for different return times (Tr) according to future climatic scenario RCP 4.5

Figure 5: Hazard maps of Tidone Pavese test-site for different return times (Tr) according to future climatic scenario RCP 8.5

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